

A NAIVE-BAYES STRATEGY FOR SENTIMENT ANALYSIS FOR E –CURRIER : FAST AND ACCURATE SENTIMENT CLASSIFICATION

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Abstract:

The amount of data readily available is far beyond our capacity to analyse and understand. The internet revolution has added to this problem by having billions of customer’s review data in its repositories. This has provoked an interest in sentiment analysis and opinion mining in the recent years. Opinion Mining is a process of automatic extraction of knowledge by means of opinion of others about some particular product, topic or problem. The idea of Opinion mining and Sentiment Analysis tool is to process a set of search results for a given item based on the quality and features. Opinion mining is also called sentiment analysis due to large volume of opinion which is rich in web resources available online. Analysing customer review is most important, by doing that we tend to rate the product and provide opinions for it which is been a challenging problem today. Thus this paper discusses about Opinion Mining the techniques and tools used.

Keywords: Capacity, Customer, Data Mining, Opinion Mining, Sentiment Analysis

1) Introduction

Sentiment or opinion mining refers to the type of natural language processing used to understand the moods, opinions and sentiments of the public regarding a particular product or a movie or an event. The availability of large amounts of data and the human tendency to always manipulate what other people think has been influential in a decision making process. This unique feature plays a vital role in deciding on matters that have financial, medical, social or other implications. Seeking second or third or many more opinions have fuelled the interest of researchers in the field of sentiment mining. With multiple reviews available for a single product and the enormous growth in the number of internet users it has become indispensable to develop a system that

collects, builds, analyzes, and classifies the comments or a review posted online. Usually these kinds of reviews are written by customers who have used the particular product or service. An individual's interests, opinions and perceptions greatly influence the nature of the review.

There are instances where people are biased in their opinions and automatically that has an impact on the content they contribute to the forum as review or blog posts or tweets. As the number of such people contributing content surges it has become a huge challenge to classify and organize the real problems and prospects of the product which makes the user to doubt the reliability of the content. Big companies rely on personal review of customers to improve the scope of their product and deem it to be of great importance in placing content based ads on sites that easily aid a prospective buyer. The same applies to movie enthusiasts and voters as more and more people are using the social networking sites, online shopping and trend analysts who after reading the reviews available decide on various issues. For example placing the ad of a Kitchen Aid Mixer on a food blog not only influences purchase decisions but also goes a long way in modifying the marketing strategy.

The marketing division of a company enthusiastically promotes reviewers by sending samples of product to be reviewed or sponsoring giveaways in blogs or in social networking sites like Facebook and Twitter. This has led to the increase in the volume of data available and the need to classify the available information efficiently as these have a larger impact. The subjective nature of opinion makes a single opinion insufficient in decision making [6]. Also, the writing skills and choice of words by contributors largely depend on the language proficiency and the temperament of the writer. Online reviews that are usually the voice of the customer are written from their angle of interests and preferences can be a combination of a positive and negative opinion which may not help in deciding whether it is a positive or a negative review. For example, consider the sentence "This restaurant's Chinese dishes are not as good as their Thai dishes". These kind of comparative opinions are different in natural language processing. When a positive word „good“ is negated like „not as good as“ a reader will also find it difficult to comprehend on how good the Thai dishes were as this decides the taste of the Chinese dishes too. When treating negation, one must be able to correctly determine what part of the meaning expressed is modified by the presence of the negation [8,2]. There are different types of opinions like regular, implicit, direct, indirect and comparative.

1.2 The Evolution Of Sentiment Mining

The evolution of automated systems and digital information in every field of life is evolving rapidly which tends to generate data. As a result huge volumes of data are produced in field of science, engineering, medical, marketing, finance, demographic etc. Opinion mining is a topic in Text mining [11], Natural Language Processing (NLP), and Web mining discipline. The goal of

Opinion Mining is to make computer able to recognize and express emotions [15]. A thought, view, or attitude based on emotion instead of reason is called sentiment. Figure 1 has the hierarchy of Data Mining and the categories of how Opinion Mining is formed under the branch.

Figure 1. Hierarchy of Data Mining

Opinion mining also called sentiment analysis is a process of finding users opinion about particular topic. A topic can be a news, event, product, movie, location hotel etc. It involves opinion information retrieval, opinion classification and opinion aggregation. It is one of the booming research topics nowadays [2] [9]. Opinion mining can be used for product feedback analysis, and for decision making to users. Opinion retrieval is a process of collecting opinion text from review websites. Opinion text is subjective information in review, blog, tweet, micro-blog, comment etc.

Opinion classification involves classifying review text into two forms as positive or negative sentiment review. Machine learning is used for text classification using different classification algorithms such as Decision Tree [1], Naive Byes[8], and Support Vector Machines[4] etc. This approach applied for review text classification of data such as movie, product, and news reviews. Sentiment Analysis is also done by other methods such as dictionaries [5], word lexicons [10], word senses etc. Opinion summarization is process of generating summary from multiple reviews. It is based on feature selection [4], feature rating [1] and identifying sentence that contain feature. Opinion mining is a topic in Text mining, Natural Language Processing (NLP), and Web mining discipline. Though user generated contents has proven useful in many applications, challenges still exist in process of opinion mining due to unstructured and noisy data on websites [7].

1) **Review of Literature:**

Since the opinions contributed by people and companies are to be evaluated, we consider the data from blogs, review sites, web discourse and news articles.

2.1 Review There are many user generated reviews available on the internet that aids a customer in buying a product. E-commerce sites such as www.amazon.in, www.flipkart.com and www.reviewcentre has millions of customer reviews for products, where as www.rediff.com/movies/reviews, www.indiaglitz.com and www.rottentomatoes.com has reviews for movies and www.yelp.com, www.burrrp.com has restaurant reviews[23].

2.2 Web Discourse A blog is a personal website or web page on which an individual records opinions, links to other sites, etc. on a regular basis. They are the fastest growing sections of the emerging communication systems. The simple and no-nonsense style of writing a post and uploading it on the web has made the blogging world an indispensable source of data in the case of sentiment mining [19]. The micro blogging site Twitter is also flooded with opinions that are decisive in determining the election results even [3]. These opinions can also be used for classifying sentiments [21].

2.3 News Articles The websites like www.thesun.co.uk , www.cnn.com and www.thehindu.com has news articles that allow users or readers to comment. This helps in recording the opinions of the people in issues that are of current relevance and importance.

2.4 Blogs

The name associated to universe of all the blog sites is called blogosphere [1]. People write about the topics they want to share with others on a blog. Blog pages [1] have become the popular means to express ones personal opinions about any product or topic.

2.5 Review sites

For any user in making a purchasing decision, the opinions of others is being an important factor. A large number of user-generated reviews are available on the Internet. The reviewers data used in most of the sentiment classification studies are collected from the e-commerce websites [10] like www.amazon.com (product reviews).

2.7 Data Set

The work in the field uses movie reviews data for classification. The dataset contains different types of product reviews extracted from Amazon.com including Books, DVDs, Electronics and Kitchen appliances.

2) Opinion Mining or Sentiment

3.1 The ANALYSIS

Opinion mining is a technique which is used to detect and extract subjective information in text documents [6]. In general, sentiment analysis tries to determine the sentiment of a writer about some aspect and also the overall contextual polarity of a document. The sentiment may be his or her judgment, mood or evaluation [2]. A key problem in this area is sentiment classification, where a document is labelled as a positive or negative evaluation of a target object (film, book, product etc.)The evaluation of opinion can be done in two ways:

Direct opinion gives positive or negative opinion about the object directly [12]. For example, “The picture quality of this camera is poor” expresses a direct opinion.

Comparison means to compare the object with some other similar objects [12]. For example, “The picture quality of camera-y is better than that of Camera-x.” expresses a comparison.

Opinion Mining also called sentiment analysis is a process of finding user’s opinion towards a topic. Opinion mining concludes whether user’s view is positive, negative, or neutral about product, topic, event etc [2]. Opinion mining involves analyzing user’s opinion, attitude, and emotion towards particular topic.

Fig. 3: Architecture of opinion mining and summarization.

3.2 Opinion Retrieval

Opinion retrieval is a process of collecting reviews text from review websites. Different review websites contain reviews for products, movies, hotels, news etc. Information retrieval techniques such as web crawler [6] can be applied to collect review text data from many sources and store them in database. This step involves retrieval of reviews, micro-blogs, comments etc of user. We should only consider the data which contain subjective data but not the objective data. Reviews are retrieved by query based information retrieval techniques [6].

3.3 Machine learning approach for opinion classification

The machine learning approach uses supervised learning method for classification of review text. The first step is to train a classifier using sample of reviews with its class (positive/negative). Then the built model of trained classifier is used to predict category of new text reviews. Popular machine learning classifiers for text categorization are Support Vector Machines (SVM) and Naive Bayes (NB). *a) SVM classifier for opinion classification* SVM is a machine learning classifier widely used for text categorization. The review text to be classified is converted into word vectors. SVM constructs a hyper plane using these vectors which separates data instances of one class from another. SVM finds this hyper-plane using training instances also called support vectors.

$$\vec{w} := \sum \alpha_j c_j \vec{d}_j, \alpha_j \geq 0, \quad (1)$$

Where α_j is a multiplier and for \vec{d}_j that α_j are greater than zero are support vectors [11]. Test instance is classified by determining which side of \vec{w} 's hyper-plane they fall on.

3.4 Naïve Bayes classifier

Naïve Bayes classifier categories text based on Bayes theorem of posterior probability [11]. If D is dataset of training data instances $X = (X1, X2 \dots Xn)$ having n attributes and m classes $C1, C2 \dots Cn$. The classifier predicts text X belongs to class having higher probability values for given conditions. This is shown in equation (2)

$$P(C_i/X) > P(C_j/X) \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq m, j \neq i \quad (2)$$

Where $P(C_i/X)$ calculated using Bayes theorem,

$$P(C_i/X) = \frac{P(X/C_i)P(C_i)}{P(X)} \quad (3)$$

The lexicon Approach predicts sentiment of review text using databases which contain word polarity values e.g. SentiWordNet [10]. Review text is classified by calculating and averaging polarity score of individual words in sentences. Many factors such as word position, word relationships, negation handling should be considered while sentiment classification using lexicon based approach. Dictionary based approach works well in short reviews text. Fig. 2 explains lexicon based approach for classification of reviews into positive or negative class.

Review text is classified based on sentences polarity score. An equation that calculate sentiment polarity of review text using a resource [2] is

$$S(D) = \frac{\sum_{w \in D} S_w \cdot \text{weight}(w) \cdot \text{modifier}(w)}{\sum \text{weight}(w)} \quad (4)$$

Fig. 4: Lexicon based approach for opinion classification

3.5 Opinion Summarization

Summarization of opinions is a major part in opinion mining process. Summary of reviews provided should be based on features or subtopics that are mentioned in reviews. Therefore,

feature extraction [4] and opinion summarization are key issues. Many researchers worked on summarization product reviews [2].

3) Description and Result Analysis

The performances of the algorithms are evaluated by many using the available metrics like precision, accuracy, F1-measure and recall. In this paper we have focused on the accuracy obtained for the algorithm. Accuracy refers to refers to the rate of correct values in the data. Table 1 depicts a clear picture regarding the recent works done in the field of sentiment mining using the techniques discussed in the algorithm.

The table also specifies the data source that was used, the feature that were selected and the mining techniques used. Regarding the efficiency of an algorithm it is very difficult to predict the best as the experiments have been carried on different datasets and using the features that the author found favorable and compatible.

Table 1 Summary of the survey

S.no	Author name & Year	Technique used	Feature selection	Data Source	Accuracy
1	Hanhoon Khang(2012)	Improved Naïve Bayes I and Naïve Bayes	Unigram, Bigram, Unigram + Bigram	Restaurant search site	81.4%
2	Xue Bai(2011)	2 stage Markov Blanket classifier	Unigram, Bigram	Movie review, Online review	92.70 %
3	Rushdi Saleh M. (2011)	SVM	Different N-gram schemes	Blogs and product reviews	91.51 %
4	Aurangazeb Khan (2011)	Naïve Bayes	Opinion terms/Expressions	Movie Review, Hotel review, airline and airport review	86.6 %
5	Kaiquan Xu(2011)	Multiclass SVM	Linguistic feature	Amazon Reviews	61%
6	Rui Xia(2011)	Naïve bayes,Maximum entropy,SVM	Unigrams, Bigrams, Dependency Grammar, Joint feature	Movie Review Multi domain dataset, Amazon reviews	NB-85.8% SVM-86.4%
7	Ziqiong(2011)	Naïve Bayes	Information Gain	Cantonese reviews	93%
8	Rudy(2009)	SVM, Hybrid	Document Frequency	Movie review, MySpace comments	89%
9	Melville(2009)	Bayesian Classification	n-grams	Blogs	91.21%
10	Songbo Tan (2008)	SVM,Centroid classifier,K-Nearest neighbourhood,Winnow	MI,IG,CHLDI	ChnSentiCorp	SVM-90%

Table 1, gives synopsis of different approaches used for opinion mining and summarization and results obtained by them.

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Fig 6 : Compare courier

Fig 7 : Review on courier

Table 2- synopsis of some methods used for opinion Mining and summarization.

Author	Methods	Dataset	Result (Accuracy %)
Aditya Joshi, Balamurali A.R., Pushpak Bhattacharyya [5](2010)	Machine Learning, Machine Translation (MT), Hindi SentiWordNet dictionary	Travel Reviews	In – language sentiment analysis- 78.14%, MT - based sentiment analysis - 65.96%, Resource based - sentiment analysis- 60.31%
Chien-Liang Liu, Wen-Hoar Hsaio, Chia-Hoang Lee, Gen-Chi Lu, Emery Jou [4](2012)	SVM classifier, LSA method for feature based summarization	Movie Reviews	SVM classifier - 85.4%

Due to web and e-currier, large amount of data are generated on Internet every day. This web data can be mined and useful knowledge information can be fetched through opinion mining process. This paper discussed different opinion classification and summarization approaches, and their outcomes.

This study shows that machine learning approach works well for sentiment analysis of data in particular domain such as movie, product, hotel etc., while lexicon based approach is suitable for short text in micro-blogs, tweets, and comments data on web. Due to applications of opinion detection in various domains such as product, travel, movie etc, it is emerged as a popular topic in web mining.

Author	Methods	Dataset	Result (Accuracy %)
Jingjing Liu, Stephanie Seneff, Victor Zue [1](2012)	Word phrase Extraction, word phrase sentiment scoring and classification for sentiment analysis	Hotel Reviews	Decision Tree classifier for word phrase classification - 77.9%
Alexandra Balahur, Mijail Kabadjov, Josef Steinberger, Ralf Steinberger, Andrés Montoyo [7](2012)	Sentiment dictionary Resources, LSA based opinion summarization	e-currer	Sentiment analysis and Summarization ROUGE R1 negative class - 0.268, positive class-0.275
Elena Lloret, Alexandra Balahur, José M. Gómez, Andrés Montoyo, Manuel Palomar [6](2012)	Sentiment Resource, Machine learning, Term Frequency based summarization	Product Reviews	Summary- ROUGE-1 (10% compression) Precision-30.16, Recall-20.54,

4) Conclusion

The Sentiment mining research is of utmost importance not only for commercial establishments but also for the common man. With the World Wide Web offering various ideas and opinions it is very important to be aware of the malicious opinions also. Based on our comprehensive literature reviews and discussions, we argue that we are actually initiating new research questions of analysing online product reviews and other valuable online information from a domain user’s point of view and exploring how such online reviews can really benefit ordinary users. In the case of product reviews there exists a visible gap between the designers perspective and the domain user’s perspective. Also that, not a single classifier can be called completely efficient as the results depend on a number of factors.

Opinion mining is an emerging field of data mining used to extract the knowledge from huge volume of data that may be customer comments, feedback and reviews on any product or topic etc. Research has been conducted to mine opinions in form of document, sentence and feature level sentiment analysis It is examined that now opinion mining trend is moving to the sentimental reviews of twitter data, comments used in Face book on pictures, videos or Face book status. Thus this paper discusses about an overview of Opinion Mining in detail with the techniques and tools.

5) **Future Scope:**

In this paper, we have investigated the utility of sentiment classification on a novel collection of dataset which is e-currrier users. The originality of this collection leads not only on the nationality of the users, but also on the period of posting their statuses updates which is the Tunisian revolution. This period was very special and unique for them, so their wall posts are with no doubt unique and encouraging to analyse. Using the most well-known machine learning algorithms, we conducted a comparative experimental procedure between the Naïve Bayes and the SVM algorithms by combining different feature extractors. Those algorithms can achieve high accuracy for classifying sentiment when combining different features.

Although e-currrier statuses have unique characteristics compared to other corpuses (Reviews, News, etc), machine learning algorithms are shown to classify statuses with similar performance. Finally, the overall performance of the proposed methodology is satisfactory, however, we would like to further improve our research by tracking changes within people's sentiment on a particular topic, explore the time dependency of our data and analyse their trendy topics dynamically. It would be very interesting to involve the temporal feature on this kind of analysis and not to focus solely on previous posts or discussions. The problems in these fields of research are many. As there are numerous languages so are the syntaxes and semantics for each language. Problems like the use of negation words and the colloquial usage of certain words in a dialect affect the reviews. All these problems mentioned above can be accommodated in the future research for finding out favourable solutions.

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